

Soil and crop management

Effect of crop residue on blue-green algae growth in wetland rice

V. Ramaswamy and S. Sankaran, Agronomy Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641 003, Tamil Nadu, India

Field experiments determined the effect of crop residue on growth of blue-green algae (BGA) during 1981 summer and monsoon season at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University. Treatments with three replications were randomized in a split-plot design.

Summer treatments were control (S_0), 10 t rice long straw/ha (S_1), 4.6 t 30-cm rice stubbles/ha (S_2), and 10 t composted rice straw/ha (S_3) incorporated with 50, 75, or 100 kg N/ha alone and in combination with bonemeal (22 kg P/ha). The subsequent monsoon rice crop was raised in the same field to study the residual effect of residues and bonemeal. Nitrogen was applied at 50, 75, or 100 kg N/ha alone and in combination with bonemeal (11 kg P/ha).

At rice flowering stage fresh weight of BGA from the topsoil was recorded at four $50 \times 50 \text{ cm}^2$ quadrats in each plot and expressed in kg/10 m².

S_3 recorded the maximum BGA weight in summer. S_1 yield was similar. During the monsoon season, S_3 was superior to S_1 and S_2 . This natural BGA buildup was stimulated by crop residues,

Blue-green algal growth at flowering. Tamil Nadu, India.

which provided the raw material for BGA photosynthesis under flooded conditions. Although application of bonemeal significantly improved the growth of BGA in both seasons, BGA grew more during the

monsoon season than in summer. Growth was inhibited at 100 kg N/ha (see figure). BGA withstood dehydration during the fallow period between summer and monsoon crops. □

Effect of deep placement of nitrogen fertilizer on ratoon rice

Md. Abdul Quddus, scientific officer, Division of Rice Cropping Systems, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, and J. W. Pendleton, head, Multiple Cropping Department, IRRI

Deep placement of nitrogen fertilizer on rice seems to improve nitrogen utilization efficiency and increase grain yield. We tested the effect of deep placement on ratoon rice yield.

IR9784-52-2-3-2, identified as having relatively good ratooning ability, was grown in 10-liter plastic pots filled with finely ground Maahas clay soil that was mixed thoroughly with 75 mg N, 44 mg P, and 83 mg K per kg soil before potting. Two 12-day-old seedlings raised in trays were transplanted into each pot. Water depth was 2-3 cm for 3 days and then increased to 5-7 cm and maintained at that level until grain ripening. When 90% of the panicle had ripened, plants were harvested by cutting at a 15-cm height

above the soil. Four days later, nitrogen as urea was evenly broadcast on the soil surface around each plant or placed 15 cm beneath the soil surface with an injector (see table).

Different N levels and placement methods had a significant effect on grain yield. Nitrogen applied at 15-cm depth produced significantly higher grain yield than broadcast N. The higher grain yield from deep placement was due mainly to increased panicle number and plant vigor (see table). □